

THE ASSOCIATION OF CALCIUM WITH BONE DISEASES

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Abstract: Diet is the ideal way to obtain calcium and its regular availability in the human body Because calcium is an essential element and a major factor important for the body and bone health throughout a person's life It has other health benefits. Through our research on the role of calcium in the body in general and its importance for bones in particular. Knowing the amount of calcium the body needs, according to age groups, for bone growth and health and preventing osteoporosis , as well as knowing the most important food products. An abundance of calcium, which the body needs in daily life because of its important functions for good natural growth and its essential role in building bones and maintaining their strength.

Introduction

Since God Almighty created man and gave him the ability to strive and spread, he has worked diligently to obtain food with which he can live, sustain himself, and maintain himself, until he became constantly striving to secure his food needs and the availability of food became a necessary condition for stability and settlement. Food products are an exclusive source of nutrients necessary for the development and proper functioning of the human organism, as food contains many of the nutritional elements necessary for the human body that it takes through eating, and some foods contain a large number of nutritional elements, and some contain a very small number, meaning each nutritional element has its own. Its importance and function are to provide us with the energy necessary for our movement and the movement of blood in our veins and with the elements necessary for the growth of our tissues and the renewal of our cells., This research deals with knowing the importance of calcium, the benefits and harms it contains for the human body, and knowing the most important nutrients for the availability of calcium, which is very necessary for muscle contraction. Building strong bones and teeth, balancing fluids within cells , etc. The name calcium is derived from the Latin word calas , which means lime, and it was known as early as the first centuries when the ancient Romans prepared lime as CaO. It was not actually isolated until 1808 in England when Humphry Davy analyzed a mixture of lime and mercury oxide . Davy was trying to isolate calcium with magnesium, strontium and barium and calcium achieved the greatest use and loads outside the alkaline earth group . [1].J - Calcium is responsible for many things It constitutes a large proportion in the human body The total

amount of calcium in the body is about (1 to 1.5 kg m DM and is considered very important for the maintenance of healthy bones and teeth in particular. Because it is 99% concentrated in the bones and teeth, while the remaining 1% is in the blood. It is also an element that has a wide range of physiological functions , i.e. It is responsible for the correct arousal of the muscular and nervous system, normal heart function, hormone secretion, blood clotting, cell membrane permeability, and activation of various enzymes. Therefore, if it is deficient in the body, it makes the person vulnerable to many health complications related to bone and tooth damage [2].JA, Skibniewska, . (Importance of calcium in daily life) The importance of calcium in daily life, The amount of calcium the body needs depends on age and other factors. For example, children and adolescents need more calcium (about 1200 mg / m) per day than young adults because they are in the growth stage. Also, older women and those over the age of fifty need a lot of calcium to prevent infection Osteoporosis Which can be prevented by increasing the percentage of calcium (1500 mg / day) in addition to vitamin D (20 mg / day), while an adult needs (500 mg / day) and the amount can be increased to (1500) . (mg m /day) during pregnancy and lactation. [3].Among the important things for calcium in daily life are:.

1. Bone health
2. High blood pressure (Hypertension)
3. Weight loss
4. Colorectal cancer
5. Calcium signaling [Wahed , M., 2019 –

Bioavailability of calcium from milk and dairy products

Bioavailability

Milk and dairy products are an excellent source of calcium (Ca) for a number of reasons , including the total calcium content in this group of food products and the ratio of calcium to protein and calcium to phosphorus (as in Table 1) . The highest calcium content was found in mature cheese, about (400 to 1400 mg / m.) In drinks fermented with milk, a low content of calcium was found (103-170 mg m), and in fresh cheeses, calcium was found. (90-100 mM Lg M) However, milk-fermented drinks were characterized by a nutritionally good ratio of calcium to phosphorus (1.4:1), but the ratio of calcium to phosphorus in fresh cheese was low (0.4) in relation to the ratio of calcium to protein, which was equal to (5 milligrams of Ca in 1 gram). of protein [Klobukowski, JA 2014].)

Dairy product	Content			Ratio	
	protein(g)	calcium (mg)	phosphor (mg)	Ca: protein (mg/g of protein)	Ca:P
Milk 2% of fat	3.4	120	86	35.3	1.40
Natural yogurt 2% of fat	4.3	170	122	39.5	1.39
Kefir 2% of fat	3.4	103	74	30.3	1.39
Buttermilk 2% of fat	3.4	110	80	32.4	1.38
Whey	0.8	68	40	85.0	1.70

Table No. 1: Protein, calcium and phosphorus content of nutritional content and calculation of the ratios between them. [4].

produces Milk and dairy products have the highest calcium availability among all foods from dietary and non-dietary factors, where dietary factors are related to age (higher intestinal absorption by young people) and gender. The physiological state (pregnancy, breastfeeding) and the state of the organism Saturation with vitamin D, diseases, or taking medications (diuretics) [5].

Mechanism of calcium absorption

Absorption of Calcium:

Absorption takes place in the first and second parts of the duodenum, which is part of the small intestine. Calcium is absorbed from high to low concentration. The absorption process requires energy and also requires transport proteins to transport calcium from outside the intestine to inside the intestine using the Ca^{++} enzyme ATPase. The body needs (500 mg) every day, (400 mg) is excreted with urine, and (100 mg) is excreted with urine [6].

Among the factors causing an increase in calcium are:

1. Vitamin D : The body needs vitamin D in order to absorb calcium. Calcitriol stimulates the carrier protein (calbindin) in the intestinal cells to facilitate calcium absorption. This means that you will not fully benefit from a diet rich in calcium if you suffer from a vitamin D deficiency, as in (Figure No. 1).
2. thyroid hormone - Parathyroid hormone : Increases the transport of calcium from intestinal cells by enhancing the activity of (1α hydroxylase) .
3. Acidity – Acidity : Favors calcium absorption .
4. Amino acids : There are amino acids that are characterized by the fact that they cannot be manufactured in sufficient quantities in the human body. Rather, food is the main source of them. Examples of their food sources include eggs, meat, poultry, milk, fish, and others. Not getting enough of any... An amino acid that the body resorts to analyzing the proteins present in the muscles to obtain enough of these acids. We mention that the most important acids for increasing calcium absorption are lysine and arginine. [7].

Figure 1: Diagram of the mechanism of calcium absorption

Also, the factors causing calcium deficiency are:

1. Phytic acid : It is a hexaphosphate Inositol hexakisphosphate , as in (Figure 2), is found in All legumes In the form of salt Mono or bivalent It is considered an anti -nutrient Because of its ability to take or reduce the availability of some important elements such as calcium . [9].

Figure 2: Phytic acid

2. Oxalates or oxalic acid –Oxalates : It is a natural, organic substance found in most foods and drinks, especially plant foods and green leafy foods Which causes the formation of insoluble calcium oxalate .
3. Malabsorption syndromes : The main role played by the small intestine is to absorb nutrients from the food that is eaten into the bloodstream. In the case of malabsorption, the small intestine cannot absorb a sufficient amount of some nutrients and fluids, such as proteins, carbohydrates, fats, or micronutrients. Such as: vitamins and minerals, or both.
4. Phosphate Phosphate : High phosphate content will lead to precipitation of calcium phosphate . The optimal ratio of calcium to phosphorus that allows maximum absorption is (1:2 to 2:1) as found in milk . [10].
5. Functions of Calcium

Calcium is considered one of the minerals that the body needs and is very important for normal growth. It is considered one of the essential elements for building bones and teeth, especially in the pre-pubertal and teenage years, and is considered essential for healthy bone growth.] DM [11].

The most prominent of these jobs are the following :

1. Activation of Enzymes

Calmodulin is a calcium-binding regulatory protein with a molecular weight of (17,000 Daltons) can relate Calmodulin with 4 calcium ions . Calcium binding activates enzymes and is part of various regulatory kinases . As in (Figure No. 3) . There are some enzymes that depend on calmodulin, as in (Figure No. 4) Some other enzymes are activated directly by Ca without the intervention of calmodulin Examples are pancreatic lipase and Coagulation pathway enzymes . DM [12].

Figure: The mechanism of action of calmodulin

2. Muscles

Different types of calcium channels in Figure No 4) To obtain the nerve signal, calcium mineral is the process of moving the muscles through messages or signals that are transmitted through the nerves to the muscles . It also helps regulate the process of muscle contraction or muscle contraction. Calcium stimulates the proteins stored inside the muscles to make contractions as required. A lack of calcium in the body can cause muscle contraction or the inability to relax, and muscle contraction can occur for a number of times. It affects a large number of people and may cause mild or severe pain . [13].

Figure 4: Different types of calcium channels

3. Nerve Conduction

In transmitting nerve signals from an active nerve to an inactive nerve, nerves depend on calcium, which regulates the secretion of neurotransmitters present at the site of the synapse and their binding to their receptors to activate the other nerve .

4. Secretion of hormones

achieves the secretion of insulin, parathyroid hormone, calcitonin, vasopressin , etc. from cells.

5. Bone and Teeth

The largest amount of calcium is used in the formation of bones and teeth . Bones also act as a reservoir for calcium in the body . [14].

6. Calcium in blood:

- 1) Normal blood level : The normal calcium level is 9-11 mg/dL (10 mg/dL of calcium equals 5 mEq/L)
- 2) Ionized calcium : There is about 5 mg / dL of calcium in ionized form and it is metabolically active as in (Figure No. 5) While there is another 1 mg m /dL complex with phosphate, bicarbonate, and citrate . These two forms can spread from blood to tissues .

Protein bound calcium, About 4 mg/dL of calcium is bound to proteins in the blood and is not diffusible . [15].

Figure 5: Different forms of calcium in blood serum

7- Factors regulating blood calcium level

There are effective controls to maintain the blood calcium range (9-11 mg / dL) thereof

1. Vitamin D
2. Parathyroid Hormone (PTH)
3. Calcitonin
4. Phosphorus
5. Serum Proteins [16].

Symptoms of excess and deficiency of calcium in the body, Although calcium is very beneficial and important for the body, if it is consumed in large quantities or its percentage in the body reaches a high percentage, especially since there are some people who have vitamin D, This means the high absorption power of calcium, and if the calcium intake increases at large rates, it consequently prevents the body from absorbing some other important minerals, including iron, as well as zinc, and manganese. These minerals also have an important role in the human body, and this in turn leads to other complications in the condition. body. High levels of calcium in the blood can cause neurological symptoms Including the feeling of depression And irritability, and perhaps weak or loss of memory. It should be noted that a severe increase in calcium may cause coma or the affected person to feel confused . . Also, a lack of calcium in the body leads

to a person being susceptible to osteoporosis This is in the advanced stages of life If it is deficient, it leads to bones not being built with the density and mass that the body is supposed to have . Another dangerous factor in calcium is that its deficiency in the body does not appear through the medical tests that are performed The parathyroid hormone always pulls calcium from the bones and delivers it to the blood So that calcium maintains its value in the blood This ultimately leads to complications for the person as he grows older, and the decrease in the level of calcium in the bones, as well as the decrease in the amount of calcium in children, leads to them suffering from rickets in the case of vitamin D deficiency . [17] .

Bone diseases: Bone diseases are disorders that affect the integrity of the bone structure and cause its weakness. There are many types of bone diseases, including osteoporosis, Packett 's disease , osteosclerosis , osteogenesis imperfecta , rickets , osteoarthritis, and other disorders . There are many factors that cause bone diseases . Depending on the type of disease, they include genetic disorders , infections , endocrine disorders (hypoparathyroidism) , bone tumors , and bone marrow disorders . [18].

Osteoporosis

Osteoporosis is represented by the loss of the mineral part of the bone and the disintegration of the spongy part of it. That is, it is a disease that weakens the bones, which leads to an increased risk of bone fractures. This means that there is less mass and strength of the bones. This condition is considered more common in females compared to males. After 3 - 8 years after menopause, bone loss accelerates , and the disease often progresses without any symptoms or pain It is usually not detected until weak bones cause painful fractures Most of these fractures are fractures of the hip, wrist, and spine . There are steps you can take to prevent osteoporosis from occurring at all . Treatments can also slow the rate of bone loss if you have osteoporosis. The picture in (Figure 6) shows osteoporosis .[19] .

Figure 6: Illustration of osteoporosis

Pa ket disease (Paget's disease).

Pa get 's disease is a chronic skeletal disease. This condition is represented by an imbalance in the body's ability to remove old parts of the bones and replace them with new bones, which leads to the formation of new bones that are abnormally shaped, weak and brittle, which may lead to bone pain, deformities and fractures. It should be noted that BAKIT disease most often affects the elderly. PKD can affect any bone in the skeleton It often appears in the spine, pelvis, long bones of the limbs, and skull . The disease may affect and be present in only one bone or in several bones It can affect the entire bone or only part of it (Figure 7). An x-ray shows Packett's disease in the pelvis . The symptoms on the affected part of the body will be as follows:

Basin : PKD , which affects the pelvic bones , can cause pain in the hip

The skull : Overgrowth of bone in the skull can cause hearing loss or headaches .

vertebral column: If your spine is affected Nerve roots can become compressed and this can cause pain Tingling and numbness in the arm or leg .

Only a man : When bones become weak, they may bend - leading to bowed legs. Enlarged and deformed bones in your legs can put increased pressure on nearby joints, which can cause arthritis in the knee or hip . [20].

Figure 7 : Frontal X-ray of pelvic PAKT

(Osteosclerosis) is a disease of osteosclerosis

Bones are composed of two layers: cortical bone and cancellous bone. Osteosclerosis is known by the term hyperostosis or osteopetrosis, which is the increase in the formation of bone tissue. Despite the increase in the concentration and composition of bone tissue, the bones are brittle. And weak and more susceptible to fracture. This disease may affect a specific part of the bone, while in other cases it may affect all bones. Osteosclerosis may arise as a result of inherited or acquired factors such as inflammation or tumors, as in (Figure No. 8). Osteosclerosis can result from exposure to one of the following diseases[21] Blood disorders.

- Poisoning
- Packet's disease.
- Congenital causes.

Figure 8: Bone sclerosis

The difference between osteoporosis and osteosclerosis

Osteoporosis occurs when the spaces in the bone tissue begin to expand and gradually thin out as a result of several factors, which is known as a decrease in bone density, while osteosclerosis is known as a narrowing of the spaces in the bone tissue, which results from an imbalance in the metabolism of calcium ions, which increases the concentration of the mineral calcium. This leads to excessive calcification, and this may be associated with pain and cramps[22] .

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